

WEEDING TRADITIONS AND RITUALS

Kadirov Alizhon Nuralievich

Turan International University, teacher

Kadirov Alijon Nuralievich

Turan International University, teacher

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Annotation. In this article Russian and Uzbek wedding traditions and rituals, as well as matchmaking in Russian and Uzbek families are covered. Wedding traditions in Uzbekistan are described, as they have developed over hundreds of years, and their rituals and ceremonies are considered one of the most ancient in the world. The article says that a wedding in Uzbekistan is not just a festive event, but a whole complex of traditional ceremonies that are held in a strictly defined order, that this process can last a month, and sometimes a year, since choosing a bride is a very responsible step for young Uzbeks. They carefully study their potential chosen one, her family and environment to make sure that she will become a worthy life partner. The first ceremony is the "Hatim", which is held at the bride's house. Close relatives and friends gather here to bless the future couple and exchange gifts. This is followed by a "Nikah", an official wedding, which is held in a mosque or at the groom's house. After the "Nikah", a magnificent feast is arranged, at which all the relatives and friends of the newlyweds are present. The day after the wedding, the Kelin Salom ceremony is held when the bride visits the groom's house for the first time.

Keywords: wedding, matchmaking, matchmakers, groom, bride, parents, tradition, rituals, ceremony, family, friends, nikah, kelin salom.

A wedding ritual in traditional culture is a complex set of ritual actions that confirm and officially recognize the transition of an individual to a new social and age level. The traditional Russian wedding is a multifaceted phenomenon, including various elements that have different origins, character and functions. In addition to ancient rituals, such as shaking hands and unbraiding the betrothed girl's braid, the wedding ritual also contains Christian elements, such as pilgrimage and wedding. Wedding traditions in Uzbekistan have developed over hundreds of years, and their rituals and ceremonies are considered one of the most ancient in the world. In this country, weddings are celebrated in style, using a variety of rituals and preserving traditions. Thus, a wedding in Uzbekistan is an important event not only for the newlyweds, but also for the whole family. Uzbek folk wedding rites and rituals were studied by such scientists as M. Alaviya, B. Sarimsakov, M. Zhuraev, S. Davlatov, O. Ismonova. However, the genre structure of the folklore of the wedding ceremony of any particular region has not been specifically studied. "Matchmaking is considered the progenitor of the wedding ceremony; in this regard, a number of studies have expressed opinions that the etymology of the word "matchmaker" lies in the meaning of goodness, the communication of good news" A wedding in Uzbekistan consists of traditional ceremonies that are held in a certain order. Young Uzbeks carefully choose their bride. This ceremony can last a month and sometimes a year.

After all, his wife is the person with whom he will spend the rest of his life. Let them be happy. Let's look at what similarities and differences there are between Russian and Uzbek wedding rituals.

Similarities:

In Russian and Uzbek weddings, matchmaking usually takes place when the groom's parents visit the bride's parents and express their intentions. Matchmaking is a marriage proposal from the groom addressed to the bride's parents, literally asking for her hand and parental blessing. Matchmakers are representatives of the groom who come to the girl's house to make a match. In the old days, they tried to choose close relatives of the groom, his father or godparents, or called specialized matchmakers for this role. Their task was not only to woo the chosen girl, but also to find out about her family, dowry, and personal qualities. Sometimes matchmakers themselves selected a suitable candidate for their ward. How do matchmakers match the groom? Previously, they visited the girl's home with gifts and asked the relatives for permission to marry. And after the consent of the parents, preparations for the wedding itself began. Matchmaking in Uzbek families:

The search for a future bride in Uzbek families is carried out by a family professional - most often a grandmother, mother or older sister.

They find at least three worthy families, which means:

- it is desirable that the family is complete
- be respected by others
- had a high social status

And so, matchmakers go to visit and meet parents and girls, the key point when choosing a bride is, of course, EDUCATION

According to Uzbek traditional custom, the bride's parents do not give an immediate answer to avoid failure. To achieve the engagement, the groom's parents have to visit the bride's house several times. At this time, the bride's parents collect information about the groom. And when they receive positive results about the groom and his family, they agree to the engagement. The bride's parents give white material to the groom's parents (or relatives) as a sign of consent, and this ceremony is called "oklik oldi"

Matchmaking in Russian families: Matchmaking is an almost forgotten ancient custom of asking the bride's hand in marriage from her parents. Previously, not a single wedding was complete without this ritual; it was given perhaps the most important place in the entire wedding organization.

When can you get married?

In Rus' there were certain days for this; it was believed that you should not go ask for a girl's hand in marriage on a fast day, on even days, the 13th. Now you can choose a day that is convenient for everyone, for example, a day off. Despite the fact that nowadays matchmaking is an exclusively symbolic tradition, many couples are reviving it, since such an acquaintance with the groom will definitely not be forgotten soon. Previously, in Rus', much attention was paid to matchmaking; this aspect was considered the most important of all stages of marriage. Often, a matchmaking ceremony was carried out on the part of the groom, although there were cases when girls also sent matchmakers to the grooms. The rules and customs in Rus' were such that a young man declared his intention to get married, or his parents decided that it was time to start his own family. If a young man liked a girl, then the parents and

godparents collected information about the future daughter-in-law, what her dowry was, what family she was from, and the like. If the choice was approved, matchmakers were sent to the bride's house.

If a girl was considered an unsuitable match for their son or there was no suitable candidate, then the parents turned to matchmakers for advice. The matchmaker was usually a woman experienced in arranging marriage, who always had several unmarried girls in mind. How did the matchmaking go? The matchmakers tried to come to the house after sunset, without meeting or talking to anyone on the way, in order to avoid the evil eye - so the signs said. It was also believed that the matchmaker should lean against the door frame before entering the house. According to Russian customs, matchmakers go only on strictly certain days. It was believed that it was impossible to get married during Lent and on the 13th. After the guests entered the house, the conversation about the wedding began from afar. The matchmakers had to say a certain phrase that meant the true purpose of their visit: "You have goods, we have a merchant," "We lost a sheep, has it wandered to you," etc. The bride did not participate in the conversation, she was supposed to sit silently and just change outfits from time to time, wearing your best. Sometimes matchmakers might ask to demonstrate the girl's skills, for example, sewing or lace weaving. Then she brought out her work. During the conversation, both parties, according to custom, tried to present the bride and groom as favorably as possible. The matchmakers described the material wealth of the future spouse, the daughter's parents, how pretty, smart and diligent the girl was. This is roughly how the matchmaking of a daughter happens.

Matchmaking in Uzbek families:

Representatives of the groom come to the matchmaking ceremony to formally ask for the bride's hand in marriage on his behalf. The future life of newlyweds largely depends on the groom, his parents, relatives and matchmakers. Therefore, matchmakers, taking on this responsibility, must know both families and their children well. If they lack information, they can turn to neighbors, relatives or friends. Only after receiving all the necessary information do the matchmakers begin their work. Otherwise, they may be responsible for possible troubles and misfortunes.

Matchmakers visit the girl's doorstep, never knowing peace, they go to her house with enviable persistence and constancy, seeking consent. When the matchmakers' intentions are realized, the ritual of "breaking the cake" is performed as a sign of engagement. An Uzbek wedding differs from a Russian one in its rituals. The bride is the girl who has a special character. Her search is carried out by professionals in the form of a grandmother, mother or older sister. When considering applicants for the role of a wife, the girl's family situation is taken into account. Particular attention is paid to those women who grew up in a healthy and prosperous family. Parents should be held in high esteem and respected. When choosing a future partner, important factors are social status and upbringing. Over time, it became common to marry into families that had high status in order to strengthen the relationship and increase the social standing of one's family. A man can start looking for his future wife himself. Only love and passion take last place. Despite this, the final choice remains with the man's parents. If the elders agree to the choice of a son, the matchmaking begins. The matchmakers go to the house of the future bride. A date is set in advance so that the bride's family can prepare for the event. Upon arrival of the matchmakers, they are seated at the table, where the elders conduct a conversation on various topics. During the tea party, the

young girl takes care not only of her groom, but also of the guests. She needs to make sure that everyone always has tea poured, and that the guests remain happy and well-fed.

During the conversation, matchmakers pay attention to several things in the form of:

- * home decoration;
- * neatness and order;
- * good behavior of the bride;
- * meekness and laconicism;
- * ability to manage housework;
- * relationships between parents;
- * relationship of elders to daughter;
- * relations with guests.

The decision about the wedding is made only after the third visit. Then the elders of the future wife share the cake. This sign symbolizes a positive decision to give your daughter in marriage. First, a traditional engagement is held, which is called Fatiha-Tui. The celebration is characterized by pomp. Many guests are invited. The girl is given gifts and sweets by the groom. Then the Uzbek wedding takes place. This means we can conclude that a wedding in both Uzbekistan and Russia is a bright and memorable event, which is celebrated with great scope and fun. Traditions and customs associated with weddings are passed down from generation to generation and are an integral part of Russian and Uzbek culture

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